

TRADE RHETORIC AS A TYPE OF SPEECH

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In the ranks of the profession, the merchant profession of trade workers is the most delicate. Because they work directly with people and buyers. Consequently, these two parties are treated through a means of speech. In this place, we found it permissible to interpret the phrases "speech culture" or "speech etiquette".

And it is desirable that trade workers use allegory and irony as carefully as possible in their speeches, or not at all. Hence, the effective use of various artistic image tools to be able to give a short, clear, concise, as well as beautiful speech gives an effective result. Speech is the expression of our thoughts, knowledge, relationships and worldview through words. The word is a weapon, the word is a peak, the word is an ointment. The word is our vision, our essence, our culture. From time immemorial, the word has acquired great healing power.

Sushruta, an ancient Indian healer, wrote: "the word should be gentle, pleasant and hopeful, and the soul should be comforted." These thoughts are relevant even in modern times. To be eligible for this definition, a sales employee is required to have a great deal of knowledge. To do this, trade employees must not only master the sciences of economics, but also know literature, art, improve the beauty of speech. In addition to the restraint, brightness, beauty and wisdom of speech, behavior in speech, style, tone, boldness, to some extent beautiful pronunciation are also important for the merchant. The speech of the sales staff must be evidence-based and persuasive, able to frame the buyer, encourage him to follow the recommendations and directions he has made, and encourage him to trade. The opinion of the trader should be purposeful, consistent, the buyer should perceive the strength, correctness, justification in his words, as well as the quality about the product. An experienced merchant book, when he is reading poetry, when he goes to the theater, wise sentences, trying to keep poetic lines in mind, it is a matter of fear that he will be able to apply them in his conversations with buyers. In a conversation with buyers, the merchant should also use short, vividly expressed proverbs and sayings about the love of life, self-esteem, confidence in the future of folk sages. In a word, the possession of a wide range of information, the upbringing of emotions, in particular, the culture of speech, is the basis of skillful

and influential word-to-word communication with buyers. Tone expression, pronunciation of speech is especially important. Speaking in a sharp, rude, loud tone in a conversation will prevent you from establishing a warm relationship with the buyer. To this end, the German philosopher Hegel said: " from the pleasant tone of the voice, one can realize the beauty of the heart of a person talking, and in the rudeness of his voice, the rude feeling inherent in him " the merchant should work on the accuracy, sharpness, beauty of his speech throughout his life. This situation is necessary for the profession of a merchant and his lively communication with buyers.

We understand the rhetoric of trade workers as a special field of philology aimed at the professional activity and training of a merchant within the framework of a culture of speech thinking and communication. This study aims to offer some considerations for the use of Economics rhetoric in the training of future business employees. The rhetoric of trade workers is based on general education and forms the basis for the formation of a merchant speech culture and communication in the structure of the daily and professional activities of the merchant. The rhetoric of trade workers helps to develop the speech culture of the merchant. The main concepts of the rhetoric of trade workers include the types of communication skills of the merchant, the ability to think, the creation of various texts, the means of expressing his feelings, articulating speech.

There is a section in sales staff rhetoric called "dispositions" that teaches the art of creating a wide variety of texts, including storytelling, interpretation, and meditation . Definitions in the field of economics are also found in scientific written texts and in the oral communication of the merchant. Since our research mainly focuses on the processes of verbal communication of traders, next we will focus mainly on the characteristics of verbal communication. In the process of oral explanation, The Merchant's speech uses information, specificity, type of product, product quality to inform the buyer about the state of the product. When persuading a buyer, recommendations to the buyer's wishes include the buyer's profession, desire for envy, worldview, and character. It will be advisable for the merchant to learn about the stages of desire of the buyer, product shows, independent actions of the buyer before contacting the buyer, listen carefully to him, politely ask about the desire of the buyer. In this regard, the buyer should discuss the quality of the product, other influencing, dependent factors on it. In such a process, it is necessary to trade, choose the quality of the product, conduct a preventive conversation with the buyer

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